

EXPRESSIVE FORMS OF ARABIC PRESS HEADLINES AND THEIR SEMANTIC INTERPRETATION IN UZBEK

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Abstract. *This article provides examples of article titles in the Arabic media, as well as their Uzbek translations. This article also provides the dictionary meanings of some words that will help the reader to improve his translation skills. The cited article contributes to the development of translation studies in Uzbekistan to a certain extent.*

Keywords: *Arabic language, Uzbek language, article, title, preface, mass media, modern technology, dictionary meanings.*

Introduction

Following the attainment of independence, serious attention has been paid to the fields of foreign language learning and translation studies in our republic, and extensive work has been carried out for the development of the sector. In improving the activities carried out in this direction, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-5117 dated May 19, 2021, "On measures to bring the activity of popularizing the learning of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level," has assumed significant importance (<https://lex.uz/docs/-5426736>).

In recent years, as a result of the growing role and prestige of our country on the international stage, the scope of cooperation with Arab countries in trade, economic, social, agricultural, chemical-technological, religious-enlightenment, and several other fields has expanded. Our country is actively working on establishing diplomatic relations with many Arab states. This places an important responsibility on today's researchers in Arabic linguistics and translation studies. These wide-ranging diplomatic relations play a vital role in the development of Arabic translation studies. Consequently, researchers face the priority task of studying the specific characteristics of Arabic mass media style and its interpretation in the comparative translation studies and linguistics of the Arabic and Uzbek languages.

This article discusses the expression of article headlines in Arabic mass media and their interpretation in the Uzbek language. Furthermore, this article serves to a certain extent to ensure the implementation of the Presidential Decree No. 6097 dated October 29, 2020, "On approval of the Concept of Science Development until 2030" (<https://lex.uz/docs/5073447>).

Main Body

It is well known that the harmony between text and headline is crucial in mass media. Text perception is a step-by-step process. Psychological research indicates that 80% of readers pay attention only to headlines. The reader turns to the headline first; the effectiveness of a newspaper text is largely determined by its headline. It is an established fact that it is easier to persuade using a

skillfully published headline—that is, through a clear thesis. Therefore, choosing a headline is extremely important for a journalist and a publication. In general, a single sentence must not only convey the main content of the article but also attract and interest the reader.

Therefore, let us first focus on how headlines are used in the Arabic press system and some of the requirements imposed on them:

- **First**, the headline must match the topic and content of the article.
- **Second**, the headline should not be too long; it must be able to reveal the content of the article in just a few words.
- **Third**, the headline chosen for the text must possess an attractive quality to grab the reader's attention.

According to psychological research, there is a specific mechanism that occurs during the recipient's perception process. This mechanism helps to process a large volume of text by condensing it into a brief form. Through this mechanism, comprehensive information can be acquired during the process of assimilating a short text. This phenomenon is associated with the existence of inter- and intra-sensory semantic transfer, which helps to anticipate the information being received via speech activity. Regarding text compression, L.M. Murzin states: "*A condensed text and an uncondensed text reveal the same meaning.*"

When translating from Arabic into Uzbek, the polysemy of many Arabic words and the existence of qualitative synonyms present certain difficulties for the translator. For instance, the Arabic verb "أعلن"—depending on the context—can have various equivalents such as "*ma'lum qildi*" (informed), "*e'lon qildi*" (announced), "*bayon etdi*" (stated), or "*bildirdi*" (expressed). In such cases, the translator must determine the exact meaning of the word based on contextual semantic analysis.

In political and economic texts, terminologically new phrases frequently emerge. For example, the phrase "صفقة القرن" ("*Asr kelishuvi*" / "Deal of the Century") emerged as a term related to US Middle East policy and became widely popularized. Expressing such terms accurately and clearly in the Uzbek language places a special responsibility on the translator. Metaphorical expressions are also frequently encountered in Arabic media texts. For example, the phrase "حرب باردة جديدة" ("*Yangi sovuq urush*" / "New Cold War") figuratively depicts geopolitical conflicts. This enhances the tone of the text and emphasizes the severity of events to the reader.

Headlines in Arabic mass media are selected based on these exact requirements. Below, we look at some examples:

The "Dunyo" Information Agency (IA) correspondent reports that an article titled "*Uzbekistan completed negotiations with Saudi Arabia on accession to the World Trade Organization*" was published in Saudi Arabia's *An-Nahar News* newspaper (<https://dunyo.info/uz/mir-ob-uzbekistane/ozbekiston-va-saudiya-arabistoni...>). In the Arabic media, this news is presented as:

أوزبكستان أنهت المفاوضات مع المملكة بشأن عضوية منظمة التجارة العالمية

Since the word "المملكة" (The Kingdom) in the Arabic headline is primarily directed at the Saudi reader, the full name of the country (*Saudiya Arabistoni*) is explicitly provided in its Uzbek translation.

Similarly, the "Dunyo" IA correspondent reports that a series of articles dedicated to important events taking place in Uzbekistan was published on Saudi Arabia's *Al Harir.info* website (https://dunyo.info/uz/about_uzb/Saudiya-Arabistoni..). The following headline was utilized there:

مدينة بخارى الأوزبكية إلى شبكة المدن الإبداعية لمنظمة اليونسكو **am** انضم (<https://alharir.info>)

From Uzbek press sources, "Dunyo" IA cites this headline as: "*O'zbekistonning Buxoro shahri YUNESKOning ijodiy shaharlar tarmog'iga qo'shildi*" (Uzbekistan's city of Bukhara has joined UNESCO's Creative Cities Network). If we look closer at certain parts of this translation, a literal translation of the combination "مدينة بخارى الأوزبكية" would mean "*the Uzbek Bukhara city*". However, based on the norms of the target language (Uzbek), we render it as "*O'zbekistonning Buxoro shahri*", because we can express meanings of belonging and possession through genitive word combinations in Uzbek.

At this point, if we also focus on the word "شبكة", its original meaning in the Arabic language is defined as: *شَرَكَةُ الصِّيَادِ فِي الْبَرِّ وَالْبَحْرِ، وَأَكْثَرُ مَا تَتَّخَذُ مِنَ الْخَيْطِ الْمَشْبُوكِ* (<https://www.almaany.com/ar/dict/ar>), which briefly translates to a fishing "net" or a "spiderweb". The reason why this specific word was chosen to mean "network" is related to how it is similarly expressed in other languages. This implies that when we translate from one language to another, we must pay special attention to language norms and the exact context in which words are actively used today.

Furthermore, the "Dunyo" IA correspondent reports that an article titled "*An international forum on supporting women is being held in Uzbekistan*" was published in Saudi Arabia's popular *An-Nahar News* newspaper (<https://dunyo.info/uz/mir-ob-uzbekistane/%>). *An-Nahar News* published this article under the following title:

أوزبكستان تستضيف المنتدى الدولي لدعم المرأة

Let us direct our attention to the word "تستضيف" in the given sentence. This word is the present tense form of the verb "استضاف", which in the dictionary means "*to invite as a guest*" or "*to host*". Accordingly, we could also translate the headline as "*O'zbekiston xotin-qizlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash xalqaro forumiga mezbonlik qilmoqda*" (Uzbekistan is hosting the international forum for supporting women). However, the translator of the headline preferred to indicate that the international forum is taking place specifically *in* Uzbekistan not with the word "hosting", but with the Uzbek locative case suffix "-da" (*O'zbekistonda*).

Another noteworthy aspect is the use of the word "**bo'yicha**" (on/for). We can provide the Arabic preposition "بِ" used in the Arabic headline as an equivalent option. However, we see that this appears in some translations while it is omitted in others. This is because, in Arabic, the preposition "بِ" is used in the names of many organizations, but in their official translated names, it is dropped without being expressed by a separate word. The following can be cited as examples:

1. **Islamic Summit of the Organisation of Islamic Cooperation**

(Arabic: القمة الإسلامية لمنظمة التعاون الإسلامي)

(https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Islom_hamkorlik_tashkilotining_Islom_sammiti)

2. **United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF)**

(Arabic: منظمة الأمم المتحدة للطفولة (يونسيف))

3. **United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO)**

(<https://mfa.uz/uz/press/news/2022/ozbekiston-va-yunesko...>)

(Arabic: منظمة الأمم المتحدة للتربية والعلم والثقافة) (<https://ar.wikipedia.org/wiki/...>)

Conclusion

In conclusion, our present era has completely transformed into an age of modern technologies. We note with regret that traditional newspapers and magazines are gradually losing their significance for readers; however, at the exact same time, the electronic forms of mass media are spreading widely. Capitalizing on this opportunity, special attention must be paid to attracting readers' interest and ensuring they remain connected to the media. This demands various specializations from an individual.

We can see that the process of selecting a headline is a task that requires distinct skill from a person. Significant work has been and is currently being carried out in this regard, the fruits of which can be seen in the examples of numerous scholarly works conducted in both the Arabic and Uzbek languages.

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